

ISic1380

I.Sicily inscription 1380

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Paterniano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140886

1. [ή φιλότ]εκνος σοφή [— —]
2. [— — — —]ς μακαριοισ [— —]
3. [— — — —] κρίσιν KA I [— —]
4. [— — — — —]HN ²piscis²
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492994

EDCS 39101761

PHI 140886

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae

Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0561 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
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